

Report on the medical imaging applications

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

The development of Neuroimaging techniques has resulted in a tremendous boost in clinical and cognitive neuroscience. Given the ubiquitous and critical interindividual differences, the amount of detail shared and required alongside the primary imaging data is increasing. While existing data sharing platforms (like OpenNeuro in the USA) and de-identification (mainly defacing) tools remain limited to the (neuro)imaging data, they fail to address the value, but also the potential risks in auxiliary data.

Although the work package title is on medical imaging, we have explicitly limited the scope to neuroimaging, i.e., medical imaging of the brain, aligning with the expertise of the project partners. The scientific field of neuroimaging is well-aligned with neuroinformatics, and many tools and strategies have been developed that are open source and that align with FAIR principles.

The aim of this work package is the development of a (neuro)imaging data analysis strategy allowing the interactive development of analysis pipelines on personal data alongside the application of such pipelines to return secure/private results, all integrated with the EOSC platform that allow expert and non-expert users to carry out analyses on public and non-public neuroimaging (MRI, fMRI, EEG, MEG) datasets including demographic, health and questionnaire (tabular) data as covariates.

The work package is organised along three main tasks: to identify representative datasets, to implement representative data analysis pipelines, and to implement a computational framework to allow (1) the development of pipelines and (2) the differentially private execution of those pipelines on that data. The specific datasets and pipelines serve as examples or prototypes and are not the primary research output. The goal is to develop, document, and implement the strategy and tools so that future data rights holders can upload datasets and future data users can implement pipelines and carry out their analysis.

1.2 STATE OF THE ART

Medical imaging research now relies on a spectrum of web-based infrastructures that range from “download-only” archives to fully managed cloud data lakes and federated ecosystems. Each model offers distinct scientific affordances but creates different obligations under the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) because medical images are *personal data* (Recital 26, Art. 4 GDPR). Below, the main platform archetypes are mapped against the GDPR’s principles of lawfulness, data minimisation, storage limitation, integrity/confidentiality, and *data-protection-by-design & default*. Citations point to representative, up-to-date services identified through a web search.

A. Public “click-and-download” repositories: *The Cancer Imaging Archive* (TCIA) ([The Cancer Imaging Archive \(TCIA\)](#)) • *OpenNeuro* (<https://openneuro.org/>), *Public nEUro* (EU-hosted) ([PublicnEUro.eu](#)), *Shanoir* (<https://project.inria.fr/shanoir/>). Depending on

the archive, data are pseudonymised or anonymised; users must register and agree to data usage terms or can download directly. While this can offer GDPR compliance by giving the data processor rights or by transferring data controller rights to identified individuals or organisations, there is no privacy guarantee against data misuse.

B. Cloud “analysis-as-a-service” platforms. In the USA and Canada, services like *Brainlife* (brainlife.io) or *CBRAIN* (mcin.ca) offer data analysis for data being transferred onto the cloud analysis platform. These can be fully open data or from secure repositories. A Data-Processing Agreement thus governs the processing and can be GDPR-compliant. A limitation of using personal data is that users must first gain access to the data to transfer and then use the computing platform.

C. Cloud-native data lakes & federated infrastructures. In such platforms, large volumes of data can be streamed directly from clinical PACS or national nodes into object storage with analytics run server-side or via federated learning, and only models/aggregates leave the node. Examples of such environments are the *European Health Data Space* ([Public Health](#)), *EUCAIM / Cancer Image Europe* federated cancer-image infrastructure ([EGI](#)) or the *INCISIVEFL* repository for AI training ([Incisive Project](#)). This approach is data Protection by design, and images stay *in situ*. The downside of the data lake is again the need for users to gain access to the data, and the limitation imposed on output.

The continuum from static repositories to federated data-spaces mirrors a trade-off between scientific agility and the GDPR principle of data minimisation. Repositories democratise access but push the burden of anonymisation onto depositors; cloud platforms centralise tooling while preserving subject rights through contractual and technical safeguards; data lakes & federated initiatives embed privacy by design, aligning with forthcoming EHDS obligations and enabling cross-border, AI-ready imaging research at scale, but can restrict the pace of research. Here, we propose a complementary approach: data are shared anonymously, and anonymity is guaranteed through computation. It offers the security of data lakes, preventing users from downloading/uploading data, and the convenience of cloud-as-a-service platforms.

1.3 OBJECTIVES OF THE REPORT

The report transparently documents the outcomes of the work, highlighting the results and achievements, but also the challenges encountered and failures.

This work package builds on existing standards in the neuroimaging domain for data curation and organization (BIDS), existing data sharing platforms (OpenNeuro, HCP, Donders Repository), and existing Open Source analysis tools (FSL, SPM, FieldTrip, EEGLAB) to design and implement strategies for running computationally large analyses on (neuro)imaging datasets on the EOSC platform. We assume the reader will have some familiarity with these. We provide short summaries in the Glossary of Terms section, with pointers to external material that explain them in more detail.

1.4 STRUCTURE OF THE REPORT

This report starts with introducing the terminology and pipelines for differential private analyses, followed by documenting the strategy in selecting representative datasets,

representative pipelines, and the implementation of differentially private computations. Subsequently it discusses the integration with the SIESTA platform, data transfer mechanisms and containerization of the analyses. Finally, the limitations and challenges that we encountered from the perspective of the different stakeholders are presented.

1.5 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This work package (WP15) provides concrete use cases for secure computing on medical imaging data. In WP15 we have identified and prepared a number of representative datasets (task 15.1), combined with a number of analysis pipelines, resulting in specific analysis outputs (task 15.2) that have been translated into containerized applications (task 15.3). We have moved beyond those tasks, and developed a framework allowing analyzing anonymized datasets (for testing and developing applications) and sampling data with containerized applications to produce differentially private results.

In general, data is classified in SIESTA ranging from 1 (not sensitive) to 6 (highly sensitive). In this work package example medical (neuro)imaging datasets are selected that are not sensitive, which allows them to be relatively easily shared between SIESTA partners during the (not yet secure) design and implementation phase. However, these example datasets are representative for more sensitive datasets, allowing a proper evaluation of the SIESTA platform. The selection of datasets aims for a range of representative data types (scalar, tabular, imaging, time-series, etc.) to allow the quantitative evaluation of their identifiability and to aid in development of de-identification and anonymization techniques (WP10).

The analysis pipelines are selected to be relatively simple, allowing easy execution and replication by SIESTA partners, but at the same time representative of actual analyses performed on medical (neuro)imaging data. Analysis pipelines have different computational costs and are based on existing domain specific software commonly used in medical (neuro)imaging data analysis, such as FSL, SPM, EEGLAB, FieldTrip, R, Python, MATLAB, etc. This covers Open Source software according to the OSI, free software that is not Open Source, as well as commercial software. Furthermore, the selected pipelines include both compiled (C/C++) and interpreted (MATLAB, Python) software, and include both interactive and non-interactive sections, and may require licenses from users.

The combination of datasets and pipelines are selected to result in a range of analysis outputs, including scalar, tabular, vectorial, and more complex output data formats such as images. This allows evaluating the implementation of data stage-out and risk-control tools in WP11.

This combination of carefully selected datasets, analysis pipelines and analysis outputs results in a number of medical (neuro)imaging use cases that SIESTA partners use for the design and implementation of the secure computing platform. Furthermore, the use cases are familiar to researchers with medical (neuro)imaging domain specific knowledge and allow non ICT-experts to evaluate and provide feedback for uptake and adoption.

2 WORK PACKAGE ORGANIZATION AND TASK STRUCTURE

2.1 SIESTA PERSONAS

The **SIESTA platform operator persona** aggregates all personnel involved in operating the cloud systems that provide infrastructure as a service, i.e. managing the underlying hardware and software resources at the provider site level. That encompasses secure storage, a 'baseline' operating system with standard tools, allowing 'data rights holders' to transfer data to the platform and 'data users' to perform analyses on that data and download the results. A full description of what the operator might need to do is available at https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15/blob/main/docs/platform_operator.md.

The **data rights holder persona** comprises individuals or organisations responsible for the datasets. The data rights holder decides under which conditions the dataset can be shared, with whom, and they are responsible for initiating the data transfer. It is also the responsibility of the data rights holder to organise the data according to the BIDS (Brain Imaging Data Structure) standard, which is a formalised framework for organising and describing neuroimaging and behavioural data in a consistent, machine-readable manner to facilitate data sharing and reproducibility. Given the specific implementation of privacy in our WP, the data rights holder is also responsible for ensuring that the scrambled data used by the data user is anonymous (and we provide tools to facilitate this). The platform operator and the data rights holder must agree on a method for transferring the data. We have documented the different data transfer protocols common for neuroimaging data, considering uploading (from an external source) versus downloading (from the SIESTA platform), as well as privacy-related issues, at https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15/blob/main/docs/data_rights_holder.md.

The **data user persona** represents scientists and researchers who aim to answer a specific research question using the data and tools that are made available for analysis on the SIESTA platform. In most cases, they are used to develop analysis scripts and code that answers scientific questions. As the data on SIESTA is considered to be sensitive, it is not directly available for access by the data user. The SIESTA platform allows the data user to download or implement the code on anonymous, scrambled data within the platform. The code is eventually converted to a container and executed by the platform operator on the real data on behalf of the data user, and differentially private results are returned. Information on how data servers should perform those steps is provided at https://github.com/SIESTA-eu/wp15/blob/main/docs/data_user.md.

2.2 SUB-USE CASES

The data analysis consists of the implementation and execution of an analysis pipeline (for example implemented on the basis of one of the neuroimaging toolboxes, such as EEGLAB, FSL, or FieldTrip). The pipeline relates to a specific research question and is specific to the dataset.

Regardless of the details of the data and the pipeline, the SIESTA platform should implement a procedure and mechanism that allows for execution and sharing of results such that the privacy of individual participants is guaranteed. One method for this is to use differential privacy, a concept with a solid mathematical foundation.

2.3 PREPARING PIPELINES

Assuming that we perform the analysis with containers that are implemented as [BIDS apps](#), the analysis can be executed in two subsequent stages: 1) at the participant level and 2) at the group level. The participant level processing can be considered to compute derived metrics that enrich the input dataset and can be used as input to subsequent group level processing, for example with single subject preprocessing, FreeSurfer, etc. The output of the participant processing stage still consists of potentially identifiable single subject data, which is not to be shared. The group level processing integrates data over subjects and can be executed using a differential private scheme based on resampling.

The original input BIDS dataset can be conceptualized as a database or as a table (c.f., participants.tsv) with one row or record per participant, and with multiple columns or fields containing the data. The single-subject analysis can then be considered as a step that sanitizes and normalizes the single subject data, and that extends the existing database with additional columns or fields. Following the single-subject analysis, the group level performs a (multivariate) analysis over all rows of the database or table.

It would be possible to combine the participant and group level analysis in a single execution step. However, when running the complete analysis pipeline repeatedly on leave-one-out (jackknife) input datasets, the same single-subject analyses are repeated many times. That is inefficient, as the subjects don't differ between repeated executions. The leave-one-out resampling scheme can be executed considerably more efficiently if the participant level analysis is separated from the group level analysis and executed only once.

2.4 IMPLEMENTING GLOBAL PRIVACY AS COMPUTATION

The following figure describes the design of the data staging and compute platform, skipping the details of the jackknife resampling. On the left and on the right are the input and output data stages, respectively. In the middle are the analysis pipelines. The one at the top (phase 1) can interactively and without restrictions be applied to anonymized data or to non-identifiable scrambled pseudodata that was derived from the actual raw data. When applied to sensitive data that is not to be disclosed to the researcher, the compute wrapper ensures that the middle and bottom pipelines for the actual data (phase 2) are executed such that the group-level results are not identifiable (e.g., using differential privacy and data resampling strategies).

Figure 1; schematic processing of the input/source data (left), scrambled data, through the pipelines, resulting in the non-shared and shared output data (right). The pipeline with resampling implements the jackknife approach for noise calibration.

For the first (participant) stage we make pseudonymized single-subject datasets to allow single subject processing without risks of data leakage. During the single-subject analysis no information from any of the other participants should be accessible or used. Having access to data from subject M while processing subject N (where M is unequal to N) would allow mixing of information over independent rows in the database, which violates the assumptions of the subsequent leave-one-out scheme. Hence the single subject analysis should be done with only one subject at a time being available for the analysis script.

Subsequently we merge the single subject results with the input data. The merged dataset should adhere to the BIDS standard. The merged dataset constructed from the pseudonymized single subject analyses should be identical to what would have been obtained if it were executed on all subjects in a single step.

Then we compute the group results using a jackknife resampling scheme. The jackknife replicates of the output results are used to calibrate the noise and are combined into a privacy-preserving output result that ensures that the individual subject's presence or absence in the analysis cannot be detected.

3 DATA LIFE CYCLE POINT OF VIEW

3.1 DATA COLLECTION AND DATA SOURCES

As the SIESTA project is not about collecting new data, nor about doing novel medical (neuro)imaging research, we have identified existing datasets fulfilling several criteria:

- 2 Have various input data types (anatomical and functional MRI scan), Magneto- and Electro- Encephalography data (MEG and EEG).
- 3 Being able to produce different data type outputs: scalars, vectors, matrices (note that images, statistical maps, etc typically seen in brain imaging are matrices with a spatial mapping to 'real world')
 - a) scalar and vector outputs should be generated from tabular data as well as brain imaging data (MEG, EEG, MRI)

- b) matrix form output should be generated from brain imaging data (MEG, EEG, MRI) only
- 4 The computational complexity of the pipeline generating the outputs
 - a) datasets should allow 'standard' data processing (i.e. use off-the-shelf algorithms without manual intervention)
 - b) from simple statistical analysis of tabular data to advanced processing, which may necessitate interaction with a non-sensitive example (scrambled) dataset to implement all experimental design and dataset-specific steps in the code
- 5 IT requirements
 - a) data must be BIDS compliant (see below), thus using open data formats
 - b) analyses predominantly use open-source software, but commercially licensed software is to be explored
 - c) preferably reasonably large as to illustrate the need of cloud-based resources

Selected example datasets are Findable and Accessible under the CC0 license. Data are interoperable and reusable by using the [brain imaging data structure](#) (BIDS) that imposes open data format and human and machine-readable metadata (tsv, txt, json) documented openly on the web.

Datasets are discussed and presented on the [WP15 GitHub repository](#).

3.2 DATA STORAGE

Input data is uploaded to the platform by the data rights holder. Neuroimaging datasets always consist of multiple files, organized over multiple directories. We have identified different tools that are commonly used for transfer of such datasets. These are demonstrated in the different use cases and have been implemented as data ingestion containers.

- wget (similar to curl) using webdav over https
- datalad (which is based on git-annex)
- OpenNeuro command-line interface
- OSF command-line interface
- Amazon S3 command-line interface

There are alternative methods that allow secure data transfer, for example SFTP, GridFTP, iRODS, which can be explored together with WP7.

3.3 DATA ACCESS

The computational workflow includes making a scrambled and anonymous (i.e., a locally differentially private) version of the input data available, to allow the data user to implement an analysis pipeline tailored to the input data.

For this we implemented the [BIDScramble](#) application. This application is open source (GPLv3) and published on [GitHub](#). The application can be installed from PyPi and documentation is provided and maintained on RTD. Furthermore, together with WP10 we implemented the MetaPrivBIDS and *DatLeak* applications for privacy assessment. This application is open source (MIT) and published on [GitHub](#). Both applications will

continue to be developed and extended to cover a wider range of medical imaging applications.

3.4 DATA EXPLOITATION

The data user is responsible for the design and implementation of the analysis pipeline specific to the data. The data user specifies as part of that process what specific results (output files) they want to have returned from the analysis. Input data and intermediate data that is not specified by the data user as a final result are never disclosed.

3.5 DATA SHARING AND DISSEMINATION

The FAIRification of the results of the analysis and the data stage-out are still to be implemented in collaboration with WP11. Since the results of any computations are differentially private, the analysis and results could be made available openly on the EOSC platform. A free or low fee could be used as an incentive for users to do so.

4 REPRESENTATIVE ANALYSIS PIPELINES

This relates to Task 15.2 - the pipeline code and documentation can be found on the [WP15 GitHub repository](#).

4.1 SELECTION CRITERIA

The analysis pipelines should impose different criteria on the datasets, have different computational and user-interaction requirements, and result in different analyses outcomes. Where possible we will base the pipelines on established analyses that have been published. Published analyses might have a domain-specific conceptual complexity that is not required for the goals of SIESTA. To allow re-execution and interpretation by the more ICT-oriented SIESTA partners, analysis pipelines are simplified, without loss of requirements that they impose on the SIESTA platform.

4.2 DESCRIPTION OF PIPELINES.

The pipelines are documented on the [WP15 GitHub repository](#). Each pipeline follows FAIR principles, i.e., it is documented, reproducible and identifiable.

4.3 PIPELINE DEVELOPMENT WITH SCRAMBLED DATA

As the data that will be upload by the data rights holder is assumed to be sensitive, it is not directly made available to data users. Instead, we implemented the *BIDScramble* application to create “scrambled data”. This type of data is derived from the input data, such that the indirect personal features have been removed (to a varying degree) from the data, while the scientific features of interest are preserved sufficiently to allow implementing and testing an analysis pipeline. Note that the scrambled data is not suited to answer the research question but should be sufficiently useful to allow data users to investigate the data organization and features, and to implement an analysis pipeline tailored to the data and their research question.

5 INTEGRATION IN SIESTA AND THE EOSC CLOUD

This relates to Task 15.3 - the container definition files and documentation can be found on the [WP15 GitHub repository](#).

5.1 CONTAINERIZATION

All pipelines have been implemented interactively on a Windows, Linux or macOS environment. The pipeline specific code, as well as the pipeline requirements and dependencies were documented and used to construct Apptainer definition files. These allow pipeline execution on another (Linux) computer where the required software is not installed at the level of the host operating system, but inside the container image.

The container definition files are version controlled and can be reviewed on GitHub. The container images are built using GitHub Actions and hosted on the [Github container registry](#). This makes the definition files, the build process and the image registry all ready to be migrated to SIESTA-specific systems. The containers are currently based on generic linux base images, but the implemented pipelines are ready to be migrated to secure CoCo containers. During development in SIESTA wp15, the version control, the container build process, and the image registry are all based on free online services from GitHub, but these can all be migrated to SIESTA-specific infrastructure, for example based on GitLab for the version control and CI/CD and Harbour as container registry.

5.2 COMPUTATIONAL WORKFLOW

The [computational workflow](#) is so far informally outlined and implemented in bash scripts in an interactive Linux environment that is accessed using SSH. The workflow has been evaluated on all datasets and pipelines and the first 80% of the pipeline are considered ready (up to the noise calibration and output data handling). The workflow can therefore in principle now be migrated to an automated Kubernetes workflow, where the input, intermediate, and output data can be implemented as encrypted virtual block storage volumes that are mapped to the virtual machines.

6 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS.

6.1 SUMMARY OF KEY FINDINGS AND CONTRIBUTIONS

BIDS as standard data representation has worked well for all partners, example datasets, and example pipelines. Containerizing the application pipelines was successful for all example pipelines, but did require a skill level not mastered by all neuroimaging partners.

Data ingestion has been realized but has not been implemented in collaboration with the actual platform operators. The whole WP15 development had to be bootstrapped by neuroscience researchers, taking up all roles and switching “hats” between the different stakeholder roles. Communication between different stakeholders has therefore not been properly evaluated.

Implementing pipelines on macOS and Windows and translating them to Linux (for the purpose of being able to containerize them) was eventually successful, although it proved harder than anticipated, for example a number of the use cases dwelled a long time in the stage of 'it works locally but not yet in the cloud', due to path issues, missing toolboxes or other dependencies, due to hard-coded file locations, etc. The interactive development of the pipelines in the SIESTA cloud has not been implemented and we cannot yet comment on the feasibility.

Since the resampling workflow has not yet been implemented in an orchestrated manner but using a combination of bash scripts and manual execution, we cannot yet comment on the feasibility of using Kubernetes or other cloud orchestration mechanisms. So far, all computations have been interactively implemented on researchers' own computers and transferred to and tested similarly on a single shared virtual Linux machine hosted on SIESTA infrastructure, as if it were a local Linux machine.

Making a commercial license available (for MATLAB) to be used in an analysis pipeline turned out to be problematic for two out of three neuroimaging partners. We anticipate that licenses for other software would also be problematic. We explored Octave as an alternative for MATLAB, but the translation of code and analysis scripts does require extra work for the data user, and might outweigh the (local) organizational efforts required to make the license available on the cloud computer.

6.2 POTENTIAL EXTENSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH AVENUES

If other medical imaging domains were to be considered for inclusion in the global differentially private computational workflow using resampling for noise calibration, then we would have to identify a standard data representation for that data. This impacts the *singlesubject*, *mergesubject*, *leaveoneout*, and *mergegroup* application containers. Furthermore, to allow pipeline development on non-sensitive data we would need to extend the BIDScramble application or implement a similar application for the data standard with which it is extended.

More efficient sampling schemes could be investigated as alternatives to the jackknife sampling.

6.3 LIMITATIONS AND CHALLENGES

Data right holder - Transferring data to the platform

We foresee trust issues (what mechanisms will there be to have data controllers share their data, trusting that the platform is safe and GDPR compliant) and technical challenges (an interactive graphical interface is needed if the data right holders are to upload data).

Data right holder – Review interactions

While data sharing has increased and is becoming part of research activities, many researchers are not willing to spend more time on shared data. In the data workflow, there are optional steps for reviewing scrambled data and for reviewing analysis outputs.

While those steps significantly increase the trust in using the platform and add a layer of security in not leaking personal information, those are unlikely to be used.

Based on our experience with data sharing in medical (neuro)imaging, we identified two types of data right holders: the same individual/research group who collected the data is also sharing them, or a different person (a data curator) than the individual/research group who collected the data holds the rights and shares the data. We note that in the second case, it is unlikely that the data right holder has sufficient knowledge to review scrambled data and analysis outputs.

Data user - Technical skills

While, in general, researchers are trained and have some technical skills in implementing pipelines as scripts and code, this is not the case for all researchers. This constitutes a first limitation from the data user side.

Even for researchers trained in data analysis, the implementation of the pipelines is not trivial due to full data not being disclosed and due to the separation of subject-level analyses (e.g., preprocessing images, extracting features) and the group analysis. For instance, in use case [2.4](#), the group-level analysis is typically performed using information extracted from the first-level (subject) analyses. Due to the strict separation between these levels imposed by our privacy framework, custom code had to be developed, which required a deep understanding of the underlying software on which the analysis is built.

In the use case [2.5](#) and [2.6](#), the group-level analysis relies on the information extracted from the subject-level analyses. The privacy framework imposes a strict separation between the different levels of analysis, prohibiting any direct transfer of sensitive data. The use of virtual machines introduces limitations in terms of performance and flexibility. Compounding these challenges is the requirement for the data user to master specialized computational and IT tools that require a substantial learning effort. The combination of these constraints makes it demanding to get a deep understanding of the underlying software. Rather than being able to deploy existing fMRI pipelines, the pipelines needed to be customized to SIESTA. To adapt to the eventuality of an incomplete dataset (e.g., with missing data for some of the participants), we worked on a solution based on the actual content of the dataset used.

To produce differentially private data, a framework has been developed whereby data are sampled and containers are iteratively called to create noisy results that allow differentially private outputs to be produced. Building containerised applications turned out to be a challenge for multiple of the (non ICT) researchers involved.

Data user - Access to software licences

The SIESTA platform or its platform operators does not provide the software and/or licenses for the software that users may want to use in their analysis pipeline. Work around solutions have to be found by the users, which may not have the technical skills to do so.

Data user - Analysis outputs

The platform and computational architecture were conceptualized to protect data privacy by design. In doing so, no domain knowledge is necessary to deliver outputs from an analysis. This, in turn, limits the type and number of outputs. The type of output relates to specific group level results. It is expected to compute some group summary statistics where the dimensionality of the output is relatively small and not commensurate to the input. Because global privacy is ensured by adding a level of noise calibrated on outputs, the more output is asked from the data, the noisier it becomes. This entails that users are limited to ask a small hypothesis driven number of research/computational questions.

7 APPENDICES

7.1 DETAILED TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS OF THE DEVELOPED TOOLS

[BIDScramble](#) is a Python-based application developed in WP15 that randomly scrambles the data in a BIDS dataset, producing an anonymous or “scrambled” version of the data for pipeline development purposes. The resulting dataset is anonymous and the results from the actual analysis applied to this data are not to be interpreted.

[DatLeak](#) is a Python-based application developed in WP10 and WP15 for the review of data that has undergone scrambling or other modifications to increase privacy.

[MetaPrivBIDS](#) and [Anjana](#) are a Python library developed in WP10 for the analysis of the level of anonymity of tabular datasets.

The [infrastructure](#) scripts for WP15 comprise several Python-based tools that can be containerized. These serve to implement the handling of BIDS input datasets and BIDS derivatives that result from the pipelines. They specifically implement the single-subject sampling, the leave-one-out sampling, the merging of participant-level results, and the merging of group-level results.

7.2 EXAMPLES OF STATISTICAL OUTPUTS

At the moment of writing this report, the statistical outputs from the various demonstration pipelines are not yet in publishable format. Their format ranges from scalar values in use case 2.1 to statistical images in use case 2.2, 2.5 and 2.6 and ERPs/ERFs in use case 2.3 and 2.4.

7.3 PRIVACY IMPACT ASSESSMENT

For the privacy impact of the example datasets that were used for pipeline development we point out that the original datasets have been shared in the public domain under the CC0 license, which allows modifications to be released. Any concerns regarding privacy relate to the original datasets, not to the differentially private group-level results that we derive from these datasets.

For the privacy impact assessment for future datasets that will be analyzed with these tools, we have a procedure and developed and [documented tools](#) that allow the data rights holder to assess the privacy prior to results being disclosed to the data user.

7.4 GLOSSARY OF TERMS

[Neuroimaging Standards & Repositories](#)

Brain Imaging Data Structure (BIDS) is a standardized framework for organizing and describing neuroimaging data, ensuring consistency across studies and tools. It supports MRI, EEG, MEG, and other modalities, facilitating data sharing and reproducibility. See <https://bids.neuroimaging.io>

OpenNeuro is a free, open-access platform for sharing and downloading neuroimaging datasets in BIDS format. It supports both raw and processed data, promoting transparency and collaboration in neuroscience research. See <https://openneuro.org>

The **Human Connectome Project (HCP)** is a large-scale initiative mapping structural and functional brain connectivity in healthy adults using advanced neuroimaging techniques. It provides open-access datasets, including high-resolution MRI and diffusion imaging. See <https://www.humanconnectome.org>

The **Radboud Data Repository** (formerly known as the Donders Repository) stores and shares neuroimaging and behavioral datasets from Radboud University and collaborating institutions. It supports FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) for research transparency. See <https://data.ru.nl>

EBRAINS is an open research infrastructure offering tools, data, and computing resources for brain research, developed by the Human Brain Project. It integrates atlases, simulation tools, and multi-modal datasets. See <https://ebrains.eu>

Public-nEUro is a GDPR-compliant and EU-based repository for sharing neuroimaging datasets, particularly from European research projects. It adheres to open science principles, making data accessible for further analysis. See <https://public-neuro.org>

[Neuroimaging Software & Toolboxes](#)

FieldTrip is an open-source MATLAB-based toolbox for analyzing MEG, EEG, and other electrophysiological data, offering functions for preprocessing, source reconstruction, and statistics. It is widely used in cognitive neuroscience and clinical research. See <https://www.fieldtriptoolbox.org>

EEGLAB is an open-source MATLAB toolbox for processing and analyzing EEG and related electrophysiological data. It includes tools for ICA decomposition, time-frequency analysis, and connectivity measures. See <https://sccn.ucsd.edu/eeglab>

BrainStorm is a user-friendly software with a graphical user interface (GUI) for MEG and EEG data analysis, offering tools for source localization, noise reduction, and group statistics. It supports integration with MRI and fMRI data. See <https://neuroimage.usc.edu/brainstorm>

MNE-Python is a Python library for processing and analyzing MEG, EEG, and other neurophysiological data, with tools for preprocessing, source estimation, and visualization. It is designed for reproducibility and open science. See <https://mne.tools>

SPM (Statistical Parametric Mapping) is a MATLAB-based software package for statistical analysis of brain imaging data, particularly fMRI, PET, and structural MRI. It provides tools for preprocessing, GLM modeling, and voxel-based morphometry. See <https://www.fil.ion.ucl.ac.uk/spm>

FSL (FMRIB Software Library) is a comprehensive library of tools for analyzing fMRI, MRI, and DTI data, developed by Oxford's FMRIB Centre. It includes algorithms for registration, segmentation, and tractography. See <https://fsl.fmrib.ox.ac.uk>

AFNI (Analysis of Functional NeuroImages) is a software suite for processing and analyzing functional MRI data, with tools for preprocessing, statistical modeling, and visualization. It is widely used in neuroimaging research. See <https://afni.nimh.nih.gov>

MRIQC is a tool for automated quality control of MRI data, assessing artifacts, noise, and other issues in structural and functional scans. It helps researchers ensure data reliability before analysis. See <https://mriqc.readthedocs.io>

[Programming Languages in Neuroscience](#)

Python is a versatile, open-source programming language widely used in neuroimaging, machine learning, and data analysis. Libraries like NumPy, SciPy, and NiPy make it ideal for neuroscience applications. See <https://www.python.org>

R is a statistical programming language popular for data analysis, visualization, and modeling in neuroscience. Packages like `neuroconductor` and `afex` support neuroimaging and behavioral data analysis. See <https://www.r-project.org>

MATLAB is a numerical computing environment used for algorithm development, data analysis, and neuroimaging research. Many neuroscience toolboxes (SPM, FieldTrip, EEGLAB) rely on MATLAB. See <https://www.mathworks.com>

Octave is an open-source, high-level programming environment primarily used for numerical computations, data analysis, and visualization, featuring a syntax largely compatible with MATLAB. See <https://octave.org/>

Julia is a relatively new high-performance programming language for scientific computing, offering speed and flexibility for large-scale neuroimaging and simulation tasks. It is gaining traction in computational neuroscience. See <https://julialang.org>

